

In Pursuit of Methodology for ‘Doing’ Philosophical Research in Education

Swami Tattwasarananda

Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira, Belur Math, Howrah

ABSTRACT : Likewise all type of researches, in philosophy of education also, the selection of innovative and hence exploratory research problems is an imperative, no doubt, but even more important, undeniably, is the methodological question that is to be made engaged in the exploration of newer interpretation of data or ideas. Hence, adoption of sophisticated logic and impeccable methodological approaches while 'doing philosophy of education' is the demand of the day. In this paper, an account of the methodology employed by the Indian researchers in the studies of Philosophy of education during the last decades has been given and an attempt has been made to lean towards proposing some methods for pursuing philosophical research which had/ have already been in use in the circle of philosophers in some way or other and which happen to be worth adopting/ employing in educational research to be undertaken by Indian researchers in education.

Keywords : Philosophical research in education, methods/ methodology/ approaches/ techniques, 'doing' (i.e. thinking/ pursuing).

Introduction

Philosophy of education itself is fundamentally an activity (i.e. doing) or a method, a disciplined or rather a systematic-sophisticated way of discerning about a problem leading to illumination of conceptual meaning and understanding and evaluation of educational policies and practices. Researcher in philosophy is supposed to exhibit this spirit of the methodology and “meet its exacting requirements: semantic clarity and

meaningfulness, consistency and rigour of thought, consciousness of assumptions and methodological awareness” (Seshadri, 1991, p. 48). Methods in philosophical articulation in educational studies which seems to be a special category belonging to qualitative research are expected not only to ascertain truths, but they are also expected to act as guidelines for answering specific questions concerning the subject of research. Two major sources from which debates on philosophical methods seem

to stem match the two functions methods should serve (Heyting, 2001, P.1).

Firstly, a methodological approach should ascertain verifiable truth of the results of its application. Because, philosophers – unlike empirical researchers – are not inclined to simply adopt a specific view of what ‘true knowledge’ entails, they tend to relate methodological considerations to fundamental epistemological questions. For that reason, differing opinions on methodological issues, and consequently a plurality of methods, seem to be unavoidable.

Secondly, a methodological approach has a duty to ascertain verifiable answers to specific questions; of course, which questions should be answered by philosophy of education is not an established matter either.

Indian Scenario: Here, an account of the methodology employed in 180 researches (which have been abstracted in the six surveys of educational research in India during last six decades) has been enumerated as above (see the pie Chart) from which one can infer the followings in terms of methodological issues:

‘Not mentioned’: If putting the above in a nutshell percentage-wise, it becomes evident that in case of 16.11% studies, there had not been any mentioning to methodology employed which may designate to either any one of the following three reasons:

- Either the abstracts have not been ornamented by the mentioning of the methodological issue, though it might so happen that sophisticated methodology was employed in the studies;
- Or, where, as regards methodology, it has been like “the works of Ambedkar were collected through his writings, speeches, letters and essays written by him in journals, his interviews with important persons and the debates and speeches in the Constituent Assembly and Parliament”, it may be taken as implied that methods like content analysis or documentary analysis, were perhaps employed in such researches.
- Or the researcher didn’t bid much importance on the methodological question.

‘Library Research’: In as much as 12.22% studies, the researchers claimed to have employed ‘Library research’ as methodology, and this term ‘library research’ creates the confusion between the tool and the research method. The tools that the researchers are supposed to use for achieving their research goals may vary considerably depending on the nature of their disciplines. “The microbiologist needs a microscope and culture media; the attorney, a library of legal decisions and statute law Without hammer and saw,

the carpenter is out of business; without scalpel or forceps, the surgeon cannot practice..... (Likewise), the library is merely a place for locating or discovering certain data that will be analyzed and interpreted later in the research process" (Leedy, Paul & Ormrod, 2010, p. 12). Thus, the very phrase 'library research' or even 'statistical research' is betraying signs and largely meaningless terms.

'Descriptive Research Techniques':

Enumeration shows that in most of the studies claiming to have adopted descriptive research techniques (6.66%) are proved to be mostly at an informational level, stopping short of using higher techniques of philosophical enquiry and the major findings of such studies evidenced to be of mere compilations of ideas not extending beyond a first level interpretation.

A sample case in point:

- "Vivekananda was the greatest synthesizer of his time as compared with his contemporaries like Tilak and Gandhi"
- "His Vedic idealism was a philosophy of action combining the intellect of Shankara and the love of the Buddha".
- "His philosophy of education was a combination of ethics, religion and morals".
- "According to Vivekananda, no teacher could educate a child because it grew according to its nature" (Nair, 1980, p. 45).

'Critical Method':

The 'critical method' demanded to be in employment in some of the studies look as if at

least from its major findings to take a commonsensical approach that rarely care for any methodological rigour befitting philosophical criticism.

A sample case in point:

- "The fundamental concepts of Dr. Zakir Hussain's philosophy pivot around certain basic educational postulates concerned with the aims of education, the nature of educands, the cultural goods and character formation among other."
- "He was not satisfied with any cut-and-dried curriculum. He believed that curriculum should not only be organic but should also be related to the real life of the educands. He, therefore, fully appreciated the importance of curriculum development."
- "Like all other educational philosophers, Dr. Zakir Hussain too realized the importance of language" (Singh. K. R. P., 1985, p. 79).

Thus, "in most of the researches so far," commented Prof. S. S. Mathur in 1985, ".....material is simply documented in a systematic and logical order. The rigour of critical analysis has not been properly applied" (Mathur, 1985, p. 198).

'Comparative Approach': There is no denying that comparative studies prove to be of great value if the focus of comparison is a specific trait of concern as regards theory and practice of education and the whole study is conducted within a well-conceived frame of reference. The following guidelines can be considered as 'flags' that mark the process of doing research by means of comparative method:

- a. *What* exactly is to be explained through comparison and how do we know a need for comparison.
- b. A frame is to be developed on which theoretical concepts may ‘travel’ comparatively (internal validity) and a unifying capability is to be infused for explaining political, social and other processes in general (external validity).
- c. The logic stands behind the method of comparison is to be clarified as a means to a goal, but not as an end in itself.

But, now the question that matters that have the researches in most of the cases so far have conducted in the name of comparative study satisfied the above frame of references? Let the present author cite a sample in reference:

While pursuing the ‘comparative study of educational philosophy in Gita and Koran’, the researcher came to the following conclusions:

1. “According to the Gita, the living being is a part of Brahma and it aims at uniting with the Brahma with *moksha*. *Moksha* can be achieved through good deeds.
2. According to the Koran, living beings are created by God and when a living being dies his soul has to wait till the Day of Judgment and then, according to the balance of his good or bad deeds he is sent to heaven.
3. According to the Gita, education should lead to all-round development and curriculum should have a wide variety of subjects to achieve this aim.
4. In the Gita, stress is laid on the importance of the teacher, but, at the

same time, it is said that the individuality of the child should not be suppressed. In the Koran also, the importance of the teacher is emphasized but stress is also laid on the development of the talents of the child.

5. In the Koran, stress is laid both on the study of religion and subjects which can be of use in life” (Pandey. J.B., 1985, p. 71).

Some of the above findings are not only unfitted with a comparative frame of reference but also seem to be factually unproven by the authentic version of the Indian scriptures. For example the statement that ‘the living being is a part of Brahma’ is not sustained by either the monistic or the dualistic version of the Gita. And when it has been stated that ‘according to Gita, education should led to all-round development’ of personality, it’s quite natural for a layman also, what to speak of about the academicians, what the Holy Koran opines about the role of education in shaping the personality. But, on this very point, the researcher seems like keeping a mum.

Thus, besides a very few exceptions, the fact that research in philosophy of education undergoes deficiency of methodological rigour and generally unfortunate quality has been pointed out on several occasions by critics of research in this area.

Some Proposed methods for ‘doing philosophy of education:

For the sake of doing philosophy more transparent to a wider audience, Burbules & Warnick, the two eminent teachers in philosophy of education in the University of Illinois took one venture of generating ten philosophical methods

10 Methods for 'doing philosophy of education'
(Prepared by the present author, Source, Burbules & Warnick, 2006, Pp. 489-501)

Sl. No.	The Method: What it would do?	How would it do?	It's fundamental nomenclature.
1.	Analyze a term or concept.	By showing its multiple uses and meanings, for the primary purpose of clarification. This may include arguing for internal or external distinctions that differentiate significantly diverse meaning and may include a recommendation or prescription of the term's 'proper' use.	Descriptive/ Diagnostic Method.
2.	Deconstruction of a term or concept.	By identifying internal contradictions or ambiguities in uses of the term or a disclosure of partisan effects the term has in popular discourse. This may include a genealogical survey of the genesis and evolving meanings of the term over time to historicize or denaturalize its meaning.	Deconstructive/ Critical Method applied to a term or concept.
3.	Exploration of the hidden assumptions of a theory or system.	By holding these assumptions up for scrutiny changes the ways in which the idea or theory or system is viewed and valued. This may include, for example, exclusionary or biased premises that make an apparently inclusive view of principle appear, in a new light, to be actually quite particularistic.	Deconstructive/ Critical Method applied to an entire theory/ discursive system.
4.	Critical review of a specific argument offered elsewhere.	By identifying formal or informal fallacies in the argument itself, equivocation or slippery uses of key terms, or identifying crucial ancillary premises that do not bear scrutiny. It may seek to strengthen the argument or to tear it down through objection.	Constitutive disposition of Argument
5.	Question a particular educational practice or policy.	By examining curricular programmes, classroom practices, funding procedures, educational laws etc. from an ethical, political, epistemological or metaphysical perspective. The point of examination may be to find what normative implications these practice entail, for example, or possibly to suggest alternative practices.	Normative Method (applied to policies or practices).
6.	Propose the ends education should achieve.	By proposing purposes of education – either in terms of benefits to the person, the society or both. This may include a broader justification in terms of social, political or intellectual ideals, or it may be more 'local', or even personal in character.	Perspective Method (applied to different substantive philosophical isms or school of thought).
7.	Speculate about alternative systems or practice of education.	By speculating about alternative systems or practices of education, whether utopian or programmatic, which contrast with and challenge conventional educational understandings and practices. The aim here is often to open up an enriched perspective on our own taken-for-granted assumptions about educational aims and purposes.	Speculative Method (For example Plato's Republic).

Sl. No.	The Method: What it would do?	How would it do?	It's fundamental nomenclature.
8.	Take an imaginary situation in the domain of thought.	By posing an imaginary situation, analyzing it, and then gradually modifying one or another element of the situation to determine which features are relevant to changing its pertinent character.	Thought Experiment Method.
9.	Keenly go through a philosophical or literary text.	By deeply reading a philosophical or literary text with an eye more towards explication and understanding of its complex meaning than analysis or critique. Done well, this not only explains and illuminates the ideas in the text, but enables us to see more in it than a first reading might reveal.	Exegetical Method.
10.	Synthesize disparate research from philosophy itself or other fields.	By synthesizing disparate research from philosophy itself or other fields (e.g. political theory, cognitive psychology, sociology etc.) to find meanings and implications for educational theory and practice. This work may attempt to reconcile incompatibilities between rival research programmes or attempt to increase understanding by showing one aspect of research in light of another. Bringing two standards of research together may also serve to validate or invalidate one line of research by showing its connections to contrast with another.	Synthetic Method.

through a route of discussions with a smaller group of a colleague, and then sent out large-group mailing lists for comments and feedback which were then subjected to processed refinement. The proponents of those ten methods were aware that “these 10 methods” are not any “exhaustive account of all that philosophy of education is”. Rather, “if this presentation is useful at all, it is an effort to characterize in a brief manner a broad range of prototypical ‘moves’ that comprise much of the work that has been done in recent years”. Thus, the scheme undertaken by Burbules & Warnick is more descriptive than prescriptive. In the following Table, an attempt has been made to present this scheme of 10 methods in a slightly structured and modified way.

More complementary ‘techniques’: It would appear from the discussion that is to be followed henceforth, that most of these ‘techniques’ have already been covered or

incorporated in the previous ten methods, but since there lies disagreement so as to the equivocality of ‘method’ and ‘technique’, the present author felt it to be in a safe position by using the word ‘complementary’ in between ‘more’ and ‘techniques’ to generate a harmonizing effect. On the basis of the experience of an interdisciplinary and commercialized African context of philosophical reflection, Prof. R. M. J. Oduor of the University of Nairobi, Kenya, outlined seven techniques for maintaining the ‘reflective character’ of philosophical inquiry most of which are claimed to be in action in educational research also. However, Prof. Oduor is not in favour of referring these techniques as methods since according to him “the philosophical method is one, namely, reflection, and that reflection manifests in various ways, each of which is a technique” (Oduor, 2010, p. 95). Briefly speaking, the techniques are as follows:

1. The Critical Technique:

The word 'critical' implies 'judging'. The idea of assessing evidence and arriving at a conclusion, as a judge makes sure of in a court of law, is at the core of the meaning of the term 'criticism' as used in philosophy. This technique gives great emphasis on independent and original thinking and using it philosophy intends to evaluate things in the light of clear and distinct ideas, seeking to protect people from fanaticism, hypocrisy, intolerance, dogmatism etc.

2. The Rational Technique:

To reason is to provide grounds for a claim. This rational technique focuses on evaluating the adequacy of the evidence upon which a claim is made. Thus, it is concerned with the logical connection, or lack of it, between the claims made and the grounds upon which those claim rest.

3. The analytical Technique:

The analytical movement in West was given a variety of designations such as 'linguistic analysis', 'logical empiricism', 'logical positivism' etc. which believe that philosophical problems are solvable through some sort of clarification of language i.e. exploration of concepts and various words in the context in which they appear.

4. The Speculative Technique:

Casually speaking, to speculate is to wonder, conjecture, and guess or to propose hypotheses. Speculation takes place where a particular kind of knowledge is not available or being sought after. The speculative technique of philosophical reflection is most frequently manifested in philosophers'

attempt to solve metaphysical problems, to which there is no simple answer (Njoroge and Bennaars, 1986, pp. 26-27) and in reflections on values (axiology).

5. The Perspective technique:

To prescribe is to recommend or to set down as a rule or guide. By means of using a specific set of principles, the philosophers make recommendations on how people should abide by ethical principles, or give a justification for the existence of human beings in groups (social philosophy) or recommend the system of government which he thinks to be most suitable in a specific situation (political philosophy) or offer what stands for real beauty (aesthetics).

6. The Descriptive Technique:

To describe something is to portray, illustrate or depict it. Some consider this not to be a philosopher's equipment, but those philosopher who choose to study ethno-philosophy and philosophic sagacity in educational settings may reap fruits by using this technique.

7. The Phenomenological Technique:

The term phenomenology refers to the method of inquiry developed by Edmund Husserl (1859-1938), following his teacher Franz Brentano (1838-1917). Husserl wanted this doctrine of phenomenology to be developed as a pure, non-empirical science by presenting a programme for the systematic investigation of consciousness and its objects. This technique aids the philosopher to appreciate the fact that whatever aspect of reality he/ she chooses to reflect on, he/ she cannot escape the subjective character of his/ her inquiry.

Although this sounds like a scheme for psychology of introspection, it may be taken as an *a-priori* investigation of the essence of meaning common to the thought of different minds and applicable to an educational setting.

A few more urging qualitative methods:

Constructivist Grounded Theory:

Grounded theory, first used by Barney Glaser & Anselm Strauss in late 1960s, is advised to be used when researcher requires a broad theory or explanation of a problem which the existing theories are unable to address that the researcher plans to study. This method offers a set of flexible guidelines that demystify the analytic process and encourage researchers to stay involved in their projects. Grounded theory is a systematic yet flexible method that emphasizes data analysis, involves simultaneous data collection and analysis, uses comparative methods, and provides tools for constructing theories (Charmaz, 2011, p. 165) in educational domain (including biographical research) also (Roberts, 2000, Pp. 9-100).

Discourse analysis: Discourse analysis is the social study of language as used in talks, texts and other forms of human communication. It is both a way of conceptualizing and analyzing language. The numerous varieties of discourse analysis (as presented in Rapley, 2007, Pp. 1-131) reveal its multidisciplinary origins in various branches of philosophy, sociology, linguistics, psychology and literary theories (McMullen, 2011, p.205); hence it may be felt beneficial in educational research provided it is articulated in a proper way.

Narrative method: Narrative method takes as a premise that people live and understand

their lives in storied forms, connecting events in the manner of a plot that has beginning, middle and end points. As a distinct form of qualitative research, a narrative characteristically focuses on studying a single person, collecting data through the assortment of stories, reporting individual experiences and arguing the meaning of those experiences for the individual. Narrative research epistemologically respects the relativity and multiplicity of truth and relies on the foundational work of the philosophers being studied. Instead of conceiving the 'reality' factually as historical research often does narrative research urge on the constructed account of experience i.e. instead of searching for how the account took place, it focuses on how events are understood and organized (Josselson, 2011, P. 225).

Triangulation -the go of the day: As a normal consequence of integrated approach, triangulation came into being as a concept that is often taken up in qualitative research when issues of quality are discussed. For maintaining good quality in educational research, the methodological rules permeated in the insight of Jahoda's study may remain as a classical example of the methodological procedure of triangulation which is as follows:

- a) Triangulation of qualitative/ quantitative methods for catching social reality.
- b) Triangulation of objective facts/ subjective attitude.
- c) Triangulation of observation at present/ historical documents.
- d) Triangulation of inconspicuous observation of spontaneous life/ direct, planned interview (Flick, 2007, p. 38).

Thus, for understanding what triangulation is, the following points are to be taken care of:

- Triangulation includes researches taking different perspectives on an issue under study or more generally in answering research questions. These perspectives can be substantiated by using several methods and/ or in several theoretical approaches. Both are or should be linked.
- Triangulation refers to combining different sorts of data both qualitative as well as quantitative against the background of the theoretical perspectives that are applied to the data.
- Triangulation allows a principal surplus of knowledge e.g. triangulation may produce knowledge at different levels, which means they go beyond the knowledge made possible by one approach and thus contribute to promoting quality research (Flick, *ibid*, p. 41).

Proposing some supplementary methods having Indian origin:

It goes beyond mentioning that Indian philosophical thinking enjoyed noteworthy distinctiveness with its emphasis on logical reasoning, intuition, analytical and synthetic thinking, it would not be out of the context if the present author chances to propose a few supplementary philosophical methods having Indian origin, though he is well aware of the fact that to handle these Indian methods in a rigorous

Uddesa-Laksana-Model of Nyaya-Vaisesika School

way requires a strong footing in Indian philosophy and for which educationist are to respectfully succumb to India's age old philosophical heritage.

Annambhatta's (1623 A.D.) *Tarkashangraha* presents a unique model of Indian logic and epistemology belonging to the age-old system of *Nyaya-Vaisesika* school of Indian philosophy. According to the scholars, the analytical method proposed by this system, through which the entire universe has been analyzed in rational language is comparable to any analytic method of sciences and social sciences today. Scholars feel that mastery in this methodology empower a serious enquirer to go deeper into any analysis of human mind and that's why *Uddesa-Laksana*-model of *Nyaya-Vaisesika* school occupies a unique position in the traditional curriculum of Indian philosophy. The *Nyayadarshana* of Maharshi Goutama presents the model in the following sequence.

- *Uddesa* – Listing of items to be discussed.
- *Laksana* – defining each item of the list.
- *Pariksa* – Critically examining whether the definitions apply properly to the items defined or not.

However, Annambhatta seems to have followed this format excepting the third component namely, *Pariksa* (Jha, 2010, p. xix).

The Dialectical Method/ *Vada-paddhati* of Nyaya System:The method in which the

scriptural commentaries set forth their tenets are often called the dialectical method or the *Vada-paddhati* belonging to *Nyaya* System of Indian philosophy. “*Vada*”, according to Maharshi Goutama, “consists in putting forward of a conception and counter-conception, in which there is supporting and condemning by means of proofs and reasoning – neither of which is quite opposed to the main doctrine or thesis and both of which are carried on in full accordance with the method of reasoning through the five factors” (Chandratre, 1958, p. 31). Besides other logical intricacies *Vada* lays down that it should be carried on in accordance to the method of reasoning through the five factors, viz. i. *Pratijjna* i.e. Statement of the proposition, ii. *Hetu* i.e. Statement of the problem, iii. *Udaharana* i.e. Statement of the corroborative instance, iv. *Upanaya* i.e. Reaffirmation, and v. *Nigamana* i.e. Final conclusion (See Figure No. 6). *Vada-paddhati* has tried to be presented here in a nutshell, but, a detailed rendering of this dialectical method which has resorted to in philosophical discussions, dissertations and treatises of India, right up to eighteenth century, gives the impression that being used as Indian hermeneutics, it may be proven equally effective and explorative too in comparison with Western

Five steps involved in *Vada-paddhati* of Nyaya System

analytical methods while pursuing researches in philosophy of education.

Vedantic Hermeneutics: *Vedantasara* or the Essence of the *Vedanta* of *Sadananda* is one of the best and most widely read introductory epitomes of the philosophy of the Upanishads as taught by Sankaracharyay, whose followers are said to number the largest in India. Vedantic reasoning though applied mostly for attaining self-realization, its ultimately resting on the light of Reason (*Buddhi*) seems appealing to all rationally inclined minds in every part of the world irrespective of their religion. The Vedantic hermeneutics which is about to be presented here possess the potency of being equally applicable in any epistemological/ ontological type of philosophical discourses. The fundamental mechanism of this hermeneutics is consists of six steps namely beginning and conclusion, repetition, originality, result, eulogy, and demonstration (Yogindra, 1997, p. 105).

Though this mechanism for exploring the inner import of a concept is said to have applied to unfolding mainly the *Mahavakyays*, according to the present author this mechanism may be upheld equally advantageous in exploring other philosophical concepts too. The beginning and conclusion in this mechanism mean the presentation of the concept or the subject matter at its beginning and end. It's just like geometrical proposition to be presented in the beginning as offering the hypothesis to be established and at the end for ascertaining that the hypothesis offered has been accepted or discarded. The 3rd step, repetition, is the frequent presentation of the subject matter in the section, perhaps

Steps involved in the Vedantic Method of Inquiry

with this notion that the concept to be discussed does not go oversight and its multidimensional facets come out with flying shades while being used in different context. Originality means that the concept or subject matter thus taken into account is not available hitherto through any other sources of knowledge. The result is the utility of the concept or the subject matter – that is the phenomenal as well as noumenal relevance and usefulness to be seriously counted. Eulogy is the praising of the subject-matter of the section at different places so that the import and inner-meaning of the concept goes deep into the mind and becomes permeated with the consciousness. Eulogy also recommends an injunction by stating either the good arising from its observance or the evil arising from its violation and supplementing by illustration. And, demonstration is the reasoning in support of the subject-matter of a section adduced at different instances. Philosophical demonstration must be quite different from scientific demonstration;

hence, different instances have to be either imaginative or some citation of former logical references.

Using Philosophical Methods: Few deductions:

- i. Thus, attention has been tried to be given to some philosophical methods by using which the philosophical researches in education in India can proceed towards a new paradigm. Of course these methods are not to be used exclusive of the earlier methods (which have not been mentioned in this study, for example content analysis or concept analysis), rather the earlier methods are in some way or other comes out afresh in new styles. Hence, one has to remain cautious concerning the need and appropriateness of the methods to be used befitting to proper contexts.
- ii. Moreover, besides the above discussed methods a few more philosophical methods/ approaches such as direct observation, hypothesis-speculation, dialectical method, and metaphysical-interpretation-method may be thought of for appropriate application for meeting suitable demands.
- iii. Methodology to be employed in philosophy of education also can be considered worth researching. Indian researchers in philosophy of education need to be engaged in developing Indian research paradigm in terms of evolving methodologies which are to be proven fundamentally Indian in nature; thus, to enjoy real 'Swaraj in ideas'; attempts

ought to be made for evolving indigenous theoretical frame of reference through which researcher can look into the educational problems.

- iv. The researcher in the new paradigm has to come out with considering the viability of using 'mixed method' of course not in a strict sense of the term i.e. a mixture between quantitative and qualitative methods only, but in the sense that more qualitative i.e. philosophical methods will be triangulated for enhancing and sustaining the quality of philosophical research in education.

References

- Burbules N. C. & Warnick B. R. (2006). Philosophical Inquiry. In J. L. Green, G. Camilli & P. B. Elmore (Ed.). Handbook of complementary methods in education research. New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates
- Chandratre P. D. (1958). Methodology of the major Bhasyas on the Brahma Sutra. S.B. Garda College & B.P. Baria science Institute Research publication. Nasik. India.
- Charmaz, K. (2011). A constructivist grounded theory analysis of losing and regaining a valued self. In Fredrick J. Wertz et.al. (Ed.). Five ways of doing qualitative analysis. The Guilford Press. New York.
- Uwe, F. (2007). Managing quality in qualitative research. London: Sage.
- Heyting, F. (2001). Methodological tradition in philosophy of education. In Lenzen & John White (Ed.). *Methods in Philosophy of Education..* London & New York: Routledge
- Jha, V. N. (2010). Tarkashangraha of Annambhatta: English translation with notes. Chinmaya International Foundation Shodha Sansthan, Ernakulam. Kerala.
- Josselson Ruthellen. (2011). Narrative research: Constructing, deconstructing and reconstructing stories). In Fredrick J. Wertz et.al. (Ed.). Five ways of doing qualitative analysis. New York: The Guilford Press.
- Leedy. P. D. & Ormrod. J. E. (2010). Practical research: Planning and design. Boston: Pearson
- Mathur, S. (1989). Relevance of the educational ideas of Atharva Veda. In A.K. Sharma (Ed.). 5th Survey of Research in Education. (1997). New Delhi: NCERT.
- McMullen, L. M. (2011). A discursive analysis of Teresa's protocol: Enhancing oneself, diminishing others. In Fredrick J. Wertz et al. (Ed.). Five ways of doing qualitative analysis.. New York: The Guilford Press
- Nair, V.S. (1980). Educational Ideas of Swami Vivekananda. In M.B. Buch (Ed.). 3rd Survey of Research in Education. (1986). New Delhi: NCERT,
- Njoroge R. J. & Bennaars G. A. (1986). Philosophy and Education in Africa. Nairobi: Transafrica Press.
- Oduor, Reginald M.J. (2010). Research methodology in philosophy within an interdisciplinary and commercialized African context: Guarding against undue influence from the social sciences. Thought and Practice: A journal of the Philosophical Association of Kenya (PAK). New Series, Vol. 2. No. 1, June, 2010.
- Pandey, J. B. (1985). A Comparative Study of Educational Philosophy in Gita and Koran. In M. B. Buch (Ed.) 4th Survey of Research in Education. (1991). Baroda: CASE
- Rapley, T. (2007). Doing conversation, discourse and document analysis. London: Sage
- Roberts, B. (2000). Biographical research. Buckingham: Open University Press.
- Seshadri, C. (1991). Research in Philosophy of Education – A Trend Report, In M. B. Buch (Ed.), *Fourth survey of Research in education (1983 – 88), Vol.-1*, NCERT. New Delhi.
- Singh. K. R. P. (1985). A Critique on Educational Thought of Dr. Zakir Husain. In M. B. Buch (Ed.) 4th Survey of Research in Education. (1991). Baroda: CASE.
- Yogindra, S. (1997). *Vedantasara* (The essence of the Vedanta of Sadananda Yogindra). Translated by Swami Nikhilananda. Calcutta: Advaita Ashrama. (Original work published year unknown).

Received : 12th September, 2013

Accepted : 23rd September, 2013